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Editor
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Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Applied Energy journal.

Title:

“Operational analysis of the coupling between a MED-TVC unit and a Rankine cycle power block using variable nozzle thermocompressors”

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Yours, sincerely

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Highlights (for review)

- The operational limits of the coupling between a CSP and a MED-TVC are investigated.
- Variable nozzle steam ejectors are used for operation flexibility of MED plants.
- An operational model of the MED-TVC process is developed for part load operation.
- Four different steam extractions from the power block are used to feed the MED-TVC.

1 **Operational analysis of the coupling between a MED-TVC unit and a** 2 **Rankine cycle power block using variable nozzle thermocompressors**

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10

11 **Abstract**

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13 the design point (which can take place at partial load of the power cycle) the efficiency of the steam
14 ejectors will drop. Also, it will have an impact in the fresh water production from the desalination
15 plant as a consequence of a decrease in the motive steam mass flow rate. It can be avoided by the use
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20 compression (MED-TVC) units using variable nozzle steam ejectors in off-design conditions. For
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28 detail.

29 *Keywords:* multi-effect distillation, variable nozzle thermocompressors, CSP, operational model,
30 MED-TVC

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32

33 **Nomenclature**

34 *Variables*

35	A	Area, m ²
36	k_s	Heating steam constant
37	p_m	Motive steam pressure, bar
38	Q_1	Heat rate in first effect, kW
39	q_{comp}	Compressed steam mass flow rate, kg/s
40	q_{cw}	Cooling seawater mass flow rate, T/h
41	q_{design}	Design mass flow rate of steam in PB, kg/s
42	q_D	Flow rate of distillate produced, m ³ /d
43	q_F	Feedwater mass flow rate, T/h
44	q_{in}	Intake seawater mass flow rate, T/h
45	q_{LP1}	Mass flow rate of steam in FWH LP1, T/h
46	q_m	Motive steam mass flow rate, kg/s
47	Ra	Entrainment ratio, -
48	sA	Specific heat transfer area, m ² ·s/kg
49	T_s	Heating steam temperature, °C
50	X_1	Brine salinity in the first effect, ppm

51
52

53 *Acronyms and abbreviations*

54	CR	Compression Ratio
55	CSP	Concentrating Solar Power
56	DEA	Deaerator
57	EES	Engineering Equation Solver
58	ER	Expansion Ratio
59	FHW	Feedwater Heater
60	GOR	Gain Output Ratio
61	HP	High Pressure
62	LP	Low Pressure
63	LT	Low Temperature
64	MED	Multi-Effect Distillation
65	PB	Power Block
66	RR	Recovery Ratio
67	TC	Thermocompressor
68	TVC	Thermal Vapour Compression

69 *Subscripts*

70	act	Actual
71	c	End condenser
72	comp	Compressed
73	cw	Rejected cooling seawater
74	D	Distillate
75	F	Feedwater
76	in	Intake or inlet
77	lim	Limit
78	m	Motive steam
79	nom	Nominal
80	opt	Optimum
81	preh	Preheater

82

83 *Greek*

84	β	Reduction of evaporator area
85	Δ	Variation step

86

87 **1. Introduction**

88 Among the different thermal desalination technologies suitable for coupling with a Rankine cycle
89 power block, the Multi-Effect Distillation (MED) represents the most efficient one from a
90 thermodynamic point of view [3]. One of the most feasible coupling arrangements is the integration
91 of a Low Temperature MED (LT-MED) unit replacing the condenser of the power block, which uses
92 heating steam from the outlet of the turbine at a maximum temperature of 70 °C in order to reduce
93 the risk of scale formation on the tubes of the evaporators. However, in this case the freshwater
94 production cannot be decoupled from the load of the turbine and there are not possibilities of
95 regulation according to the electricity and water demands of the location. The integration of Thermal
96 Vapour Compression (MED-TVC) units into Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants has a major
97 advantage with respect that one: the possibility of decoupling the fresh water and power productions,
98 which provides more flexibility to the operation of the plant and permits to adapt both productions to
99 the daily or seasonal demands. In addition, there is no need to replace the condenser of the power
100 cycle as in the case of the LT-MED and it allows the steam to be expanded completely through the
101 turbine. Moreover, the thermal efficiency the MED-TVC unit is significantly increased with respect
102 the LT-MED plants. In the CSP+MED-TVC configuration, the coupling with a power block is made
103 through one of the steam extractions of the turbines, being the steam used as motive steam for the
104 ejectors.

105 Most of the MED-TVC plants use conventional thermocompressors, which are designed for a fixed
106 motive steam pressure and can only operate at an acceptable efficiency with motive steam pressures
107 close to the nominal. When these plants are integrated into a power plant, it is needed to adapt the
108 steam ejectors to the operation of the power block (the part load operation of the power block leads
109 to changes in the pressure of the steam extractions from the turbine), which is only possible with the
110 use of variable nozzle thermocompressors. They are able to modify the motive steam mass flow rate
111 with a spindle located inside the nozzle, which changes its cross sectional area. Thus, the mass flow
112 rate of motive steam can be kept constant or varied for convenience when the motive steam pressure
113 changes at part load conditions, operating always with the maximum possible efficiency.

114 Although the literature related with the use of variable nozzle thermocompressors is scarce, the
115 advantages of this kind of ejectors in MED desalination plants using steam from a power plant have
116 been already pointed out by several authors. Desportes [4] showed its use in the Huanghua Project in
117 China. In that project, which was aimed to produce both power and water, a combined cycle power
118 plant with two generation blocks of 600 MW fed two MED-TVC units with 4 effects and a capacity
119 of 10,000 m³/d each, using steam from the medium pressure turbines of the power plant. A variable
120 nozzle thermocompressor was implemented for the MED-TVC units, permitting to adjust or keep the
121 motive steam mass flow rate constant when the pressure of the steam extracted from the turbines
122 varies. In such way, the thermocompressor could be operated always with the maximum efficiency

123 possible at the given pressure. Also, Shemmer [5] described the issues found in the operation process
124 of a MED-TVC unit integrated with a coal-fired power plant in Tianjin (China), particularly the
125 changes in the motive steam pressure as result of the decrease in the power demand, being the power
126 block controlled with the sliding pressure method. This was solved by introducing variable nozzle
127 thermocompressors that could handle the variable pressures maintaining always a high efficiency.
128 Efrat and Haimiao [6] also presented the benefits of the design of the MED-TVC plant in the above-
129 mentioned power plant in Tianjin, which integrates the production of power, freshwater and brine.
130 They underlined the great flexibility of operation achieved thanks to the variable nozzle
131 thermocompressors, providing a high efficiency in the power, freshwater and brine production. The
132 importance of using thermocompressors with adjustable cross sectional area of the nozzle has been
133 also highlighted by other authors [7,8], because of their capacity of working with high efficiency in a
134 wide range of motive steam pressure conditions.

135 None of the above studies have analysed deeply the operation of a MED-TVC unit integrated into a
136 CSP plant using variable nozzle thermocompressors. This paper analyses the operation limits and the
137 performance of the desalination unit at different thermal loads of a Rankine cycle power block. To
138 that end, a parametric study of the MED-TVC unit at part load operation has been carried out, taking
139 into account the variation of the motive steam pressure as a result of the decrease in the power
140 demand. Moreover, the strategy followed to simulate the off-design operation of the MED-TVC unit
141 and its effect on the main performance variables is presented.

142 **2. Modelling of the system**

143 **2.1. Rankine cycle power block**

144 A 50 MW_e Rankine cycle power block has been modelled in Thermoflex® [9], a software which
145 enables to investigate the power production with high accuracy at design and off-design conditions.
146 The power block (see Figure 1) is a single reheat, regenerative Rankine cycle with six feedwater
147 heaters (FWH) with the same configuration as the commercial solar thermal power plant Andasol-1
148 [1]. Table 1 shows the main parameters of the power block. The feedwater is preheated in three low-
149 pressure feedwater heaters (LP P1, LP P2, LP P3), in a deaerator and in two high-pressure feed water
150 heaters (HP P1, HP P2). The steam generator, which integrates the economizer, boiler and super-
151 heater, has an efficiency of 98% and a 4.5 bar pressure drop and it delivers the superheated steam at
152 90 bar and 370 °C to a high pressure (HP) turbine. The second high pressure preheater (HP P2) is fed
153 by a 45.4 bar steam extraction from the HP expansion line. The remaining stream expands until 20.6
154 bar. A second extraction point, which feeds HP P1, matches the HP turbine outlet. A reheater
155 increases the steam temperature to 370 °C before the low pressure (LP) expansion line. Both HP and
156 LP turbines are regulated with the *sliding pressure* mode, thus maintaining the temperature of the

157 steam entering the HP turbine constant at partial load while decreasing the pressure and mass flow
158 rate of steam. Therefore, the steam generator and reheater are modelled to provide the nominal steam
159 temperature of 370 °C in both design and off-design conditions. Four steam extractions from the LP
160 turbine feed the deaerator and three LP feedwater heaters. LP expansion line is split in five turbine
161 stages in which steam expands from 18.18 bar and 370 °C to 0.08 bar (water-cooled condenser
162 operative pressure). The inlet pressure for each stage of the turbines is set according to Stodola law,
163 where the following ratio is determined as follows:

$$q \cdot \frac{\sqrt{T_{in}}}{p_{in}} = const \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

164 being q the steam mass flow rate at the inlet of each stage, T_{in} and p_{in} are the inlet steam
165 temperature and pressure in each turbine stage, respectively.

166 Different configurations have been selected for the integration of the MED-TVC unit into the power
167 block. Each one considers that part of the steam extracted from the turbine is taken as motive steam
168 to feed the thermocompressor coupled to the desalination plant, returning the condensed vapour from
169 the first effect of the MED plant to the condenser of the power block as subcooled liquid. In this way,
170 four configurations results from integrating the MED-TVC unit to the following steam extractions of
171 the power block: 45.4, 20.6, 8.75 and 3.627 bar, corresponding to HP2, HP1, DEA and LP3,
172 respectively. In all cases, the steam mass flow rate entering in the HP turbine at design conditions has
173 been considered as input of the model (63.42 kg/s), which has been taken equal to that used in a plant
174 similar to Andasol-1 [1].

175 Simulations of the power block have been performed for a wide range of thermal loads, from 120%
176 to 20% (the technical minimum of the steam turbines operation is about 15–20% [10]), in order to
177 study the limit load that allows a constant motive steam mass flow rate for the thermocompressor
178 equal to the one at nominal conditions, and therefore an on-design operation of the MED-TVC plant.
179 From the limit load onwards, the motive steam mass flow rate to the thermocompressor of the MED-
180 TVC unit was reduced and the simulations of the power block were performed until the minimum
181 achievable load of the power block was obtained (that one that allows the convergence of the model).

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Figure 1. Diagram of the power block model in Thermoflex.

Table 1. Main parameters of the power block at nominal conditions [1].

Parameter	Value
<i>Turbines</i>	
HP inlet temperature (°C)	370
HP inlet pressure (bar)	90
High pressure turbine efficiency (%)	85.5
Low pressure turbine efficiency (%)	89.5
Electro-mechanical efficiency (%)	98
<i>Condenser</i>	
Pressure (bar)	0.08
<i>Extraction point pressures</i>	
Extraction line HP2 (bar)	45.4
Extraction line HP1 (bar)	20.6
Extraction line DEA (bar)	8.75
Extraction line LP3 (bar)	3.627
Extraction line LP2 (bar)	1.224
Extraction line LP1 (bar)	0.3461
<i>Pressure drop</i>	
Extraction line HP2 (%)	2.5
Extraction line HP1 (%)	3
Extraction line DEA (%)	4.5

Extraction line LP3 (%)	3
Extraction line LP2 (%)	3
Extraction line LP1 (%)	3.5
Reheating line (%)	11.75
<i>Condenser pump</i>	
Isentropic efficiency (%)	75
Electro-mechanical efficiency (%)	98
<i>Feedwater pump</i>	
Isentropic efficiency (%)	78
Electro-mechanical efficiency (%)	98
<i>Closed feedwater heaters</i>	
Terminal temperature difference (°C)	1.5
Drain cooling approach (°C)	5
<i>Steam generator</i>	
Thermal efficiency (%)	98
Total pressure drop (water side) (bar)	4.5

187

188 **2.2. Multi-effect distillation with thermal vapour compression unit**

189 *2.2.1. Process description*

190 The multi-effect distillation technology for seawater desalination is based on consecutive processes
191 of evaporation of the seawater and subsequent condensation of the generated vapour. These
192 processes take place inside connected vessels, called effects, each one at a pressure lower than the
193 previous one, in order to be able to reuse the latent heat of the vapour. In general, each effect is
194 comprised of a falling film evaporator, a demister, a preheater and a flash box. In the parallel/cross
195 feed configuration (the one used in this study), the feedwater enters each effect at the same time,
196 after being warmed up in the preheaters. The only external thermal energy addition occurs in the first
197 evaporator, usually using saturated vapour (called heating steam) at a temperature below 70 °C to
198 avoid the appearance of scaling over the external surface of the tubes. The feedwater entering the
199 first effect is sprayed over the tube bundle of the evaporator, generating a thin falling film that boils
200 as consequence of the heat released by the condensation of the heating steam inside the tubes. On
201 one hand, vapour, which is considered free of salts, is produced, and on the other hand, concentrated
202 brine is deposited at the bottom of the effect and driven to the next effect, where is mixed with the
203 brine of such effect. In this process a small amount of flash vapour is produced, which contributes to
204 the total amount of vapour generated in the effect. Part of the total vapour generated condenses in the

205 preheater, warming up the feedwater, and the rest is directed inside the tubes of the next evaporator
206 and used as the driving force of the following evaporation-condensation process, at lower
207 temperature and pressure. For a generic intermediate effect, the steam condensed in the associated
208 preheater along with the steam condensed inside the evaporator are driven to the corresponding flash
209 box, where they are collected, generating additional vapour by flash. This sequence is repeated until
210 the last effect, where the remaining vapour releases its latent heat in the end condenser, which is used
211 as the refrigeration system of the process.

212 One important component of a MED-TVC unit is the thermocompressor, which is a simple device
213 that compresses low pressure vapour (suction or entrainment steam) using high pressure vapour
214 (motive steam) by means of the well-known Venturi effect. It has three main sections: in the first
215 convergent section, the fluid is accelerated creating a pressure decrease that drags the entrainment
216 vapour into the middle section, called mixing zone. After that, in the divergent section, the mixed
217 vapour is decelerated and its pressure elevated up to an intermediate pressure between the motive
218 steam pressure and the entrainment vapour pressure. Variable nozzle thermocompressors (Figure 2)
219 are able to cope with a wide broad of operating conditions maintaining a good performance, because
220 of their ability to keep the motive steam flow rate constant when the pressure decreases. This is done
221 with a spindle inside the nozzle that moves back and forth and changes the cross sectional area,
222 letting pass a higher/lower amount of motive steam. That is why the concept of variable nozzle
223 thermocompressors is so interesting in dual purpose power plants.
224

225

226

Figure 2. Scheme of variable nozzle thermocompressors.

227

2.2.2. Model of the MED-TVC unit

228 The desalination plant considered is a parallel/cross multi-effect distillation system with thermal
229 vapour compression based on the MED-TVC commercial plant located in Trapani (Italy) [2] (see
230 Figure 3). This plant comprises four MED-TVC units of 12 effects and a preheater every two effects,
231 and it is fed with high pressure steam at 45 bar from a boiler. In addition, it has two plate heat

232 exchangers at the inlet of the plant in order to deal with the different temperatures of the intake
 233 seawater during the year (22 – 10 °C). All the design data of the plant modelled are indicated in
 234 Table 2. The unit has been designed in order to minimize the thermodynamic losses of the vapour
 235 during the condensation process, selecting appropriate values of the geometrical features, such as: the
 236 diameter of the connecting lines between the effects, diameter of the tubes in the evaporators, density
 237 of the demisters, etc. Notice that the maximum salinity of the brine in the design has been limited to
 238 65,900 ppm in order to avoid scaling in the tubes.

239

240

241

Figure 3. Diagram of the MED-TVC unit considered.

242

243

Table 2. Design data of the MED-TVC unit. Reference [2] except otherwise indicated.

Concept	Value
<i>Design and operational parameters</i>	
Design capacity (m ³ /d)	10,000
Number of effects	12
Thermocompressor location	12 th
Motive steam pressure (bar)	45.4
Heating steam temperature (°C)	70
Brine temperature in the last effect (°C)	37
Intake seawater temperature (°C)	22
Intake seawater salinity (ppm)	40,000
Maximum salinity in the first effect (ppm)	65,900
Feed seawater temperature (°C)	35

Inlet seawater temperature (°C)	25.9
Feedwater temperature at 1 st effect ^a (°C)	60
Distillate temperature ^a (°C)	25
<i>Connecting lines</i>	
Diameter of the connecting lines (mm)	1000
Tube longitude between effects (m)	2
<i>Tube bundle evaporators</i>	
Tube longitude of the evaporators (m) [11]	7
External diameter of evaporator tubes (m) [11]	0.022
Internal diameter of evaporator tubes (m) [11]	0.018
<i>Demisters</i>	
Wire diameter of the demister (mm) [12]	0.32
Density of the demister (kg/m ³) [12]	100
Mesh pad thickness of the demister (m) [12]	0.1
Vessel diameter ^a (m)	4.8

^a Assumption

244

245 In order to perform the simulations of the MED-TVC unit coupled to the power block, a design and
246 an operational model for the MED-TVC unit are required, which are described below. The first one
247 is used to size and characterize the different components of the plant, such as the areas of the
248 evaporators, preheaters and end condenser, the location of the thermocompressor, the nominal
249 motive steam mass flow rate, etc., for each configuration. Once those parameters are obtained, the
250 operational model permit to simulate the unit in operation, based on a fixed geometry, with changing
251 conditions of the motive steam.

252 Regarding the model of the thermocompressor, the curves from Power [13], which provides the
253 entrainment ratio (ratio between the motive steam and suction steam mass flow rates) as function of
254 the compression and expansion ratios, have been selected. The equations from these curves have
255 been obtained by Ashraf and Darwish and are shown in [14]. This model is particularly appropriate
256 for simulating variable nozzle thermocompressors as it is valid for a wide range of motive steam
257 pressures.

258 2.2.3. Design model of the MED-TVC unit

259 As mentioned above, four different coupling arrangements of the MED-TVC unit with the power
260 block have been considered, corresponding to four steam extractions (namely HP2, HP1, DEA and
261 LP3). For each coupling arrangement, the location of the thermocompressor that provides a
262 maximum *GOR* and a minimum specific heat transfer area (determining the optimum reduction of the
263 area of the evaporators after the thermocompressor location) was obtained in an exhaustive study
264 presented by Ortega-Delgado et al. [15]. In that paper, a complete and detailed description of the

265 design model of the MED-TVC unit developed and implemented in Engineering Equation Solver
 266 (EES) environment [16], along with the assumptions and approximations made, can be found. The
 267 main results obtained from this study can be seen in Table 3. The nominal motive steam mass flow
 268 rate (q_m) obtained in the design model was used in the model of the power block for the simulations.
 269 Also, this variable together with the thermocompressor location, the optimum reduction of the
 270 evaporators area after the thermocompressor location (β_{opt}), the area of the evaporators before the
 271 thermocompressor location (A_{bef}), the area of preheaters (A_{preh}), the area of end condenser (A_c), the
 272 feedwater mass flow rate (q_F) and the rejected cooling seawater mass flow rate (q_{cw}) were used as
 273 inputs for the operational model of the MED-TVC unit.

274 **Table 3.** MED-TVC nominal design for the four motive steam pressures considered.

p_m (bar)	TC (-)	sA (m ² s)/kg	GOR (-)	q_D (m ³ /d)	q_m (kg/s)	q_F (T/h)	q_{cw} (T/h)	CR (-)	β_{opt} (-)	A_{bef} (m ²)	A_{preh} (m ²)	A_c (m ²)
45.4	11	526	14.67	9823	7.691	1300	275.9	4.49	0.7	4839	149.9	1957
20.6	10	521.5	14.2	9593	7.757	1273	325.6	3.95	0.653	4839	149.9	1986
8.75	9	516.2	13.78	9344	7.785	1243	349.7	3.5	0.627	4839	149.9	1977
3.627	9	520	12.86	9384	8.377	1245	459.3	3.47	0.662	4839	149.9	2123

275 *2.2.4. Operational model of the MED-TVC unit*

276 In order to simulate the off-design conditions (also called partial load) of the MED-TVC unit, an
 277 operational model based on the design model was developed. The MED-TVC plant operates at
 278 partial load when the mass flow rate or pressure of the motive steam changes, since it results in a
 279 variation of the external thermal energy supplied to the plant (heating steam mass flow rate and
 280 temperature). This occurs either when the motive steam pressure is reduced as consequence of the
 281 sliding pressure regulation of the power block or when there is not enough steam available in the
 282 power block to feed the MED-TVC unit with the nominal motive steam mass flow rate. It was
 283 considered that there was not available motive steam to feed the MED-TVC unit at nominal
 284 conditions when the mass flow rate of steam entering the LP P1 feedwater heater is lower than 0.1
 285 kg/s. At these conditions, the mass flow rate of motive steam has to be decreased. The operation of
 286 the MED-TVC unit has been considered between 100 and 40% of the rated load, in accordance with
 287 Shemer [5].

288 As explained before, in the operational model, the heat transfer areas have been taken as input
 289 variables and equal to those ones obtained from the design model (Table 3). Also, the feedwater
 290 mass flow rate (q_F) obtained by the design model for each case has been taken as initial value for the
 291 operational model. This variable, along with the heating steam temperature, have been considered as
 292 control variables in the operational model to adjust the salinity of the brine in the first effect and the

293 brine temperature in the last effect, respectively. Their variation is consequence of the off-design
 294 operation of the power block, which is explained hereafter.

295 In order to see the effect of the partial load operation of the power block on the feedwater mass flow
 296 rate and this one on the brine salinity, the case of the MED-TVC unit operating with motive steam
 297 pressure at 45.4 bar has been investigated. As observed in Figure 4, a decrease of the motive steam
 298 mass flow rate from its nominal value (7.691 kg/s) results in an increase in the brine salinity in the
 299 first effect up to a limit of 120,000 ppm (it is the validity limit of the correlation used for the
 300 calculation of the seawater's thermo-physical properties), which can provoke serious scale formation
 301 risks. The increase in the brine salinity is due to the reduction of the feedwater flow rate entering the
 302 plant, which is caused by the decrease in the motive steam mass flow rate. This reduction leads to a
 303 decrease in the heat rate in the evaporator of the first effect and therefore in the compressed steam
 304 mass flow rate (as shown in Figure 5), reducing the feedwater flow rate needed in the process. On the
 305 other hand, the end condenser temperature is also affected by the decrease in the motive steam mass
 306 flow rate, since the lower amount of vapour produced in each effect (as a consequence of a lower
 307 heat rate in the first evaporator) leads to lower cooling needs in the end condenser of the MED plant
 308 (as depicted in Figure 6) and therefore to an increase of the condensation temperature. It can have a
 309 significant effect on the distillate produced (as seen in Figure 6) since the temperature differences
 310 between effects are reduced and therefore the driving force of the evaporation process is decreased.

311

312 **Figure 4.** Variation of the brine salinity in the first effect and feedwater mass flow rate with the
 313 motive steam mass flow rate, for $p_m = 45.4$ bar.

314

315 **Figure 5.** Variation of the heat rate in the first effect (Q_1) and the compressed steam mass flow rate
 316 (q_{comp}) with the motive steam mass flow rate, for $p_m = 45.4$ bar.

317

318 **Figure 6.** Variation of the daily freshwater production and mass flow rate of intake seawater with the
 319 motive steam mass flow rate, for $p_m = 45.4$ bar.

320 In order to avoid scale formation and a decrease in the distillate production, both variables (brine
 321 salinity and end condenser temperature) have to be controlled by a proper variation in the feedwater

322 flowrate and heating steam temperature, respectively. Accordingly, on one hand q_F is adjusted in
323 order to maintain the brine salinity in the first and second effects below a certain limit (70,000 ppm).
324 On the other hand, the heating steam temperature (T_s) is adjusted within 70 and 60 °C (minimum
325 temperature which leads to a reasonable temperature difference between effects, close to 2 °C) in
326 order to maintain the condensation temperature around its design value, 37 °C.

327 The adjustment of q_F has been done by developing an algorithm (see Figure 7) that has been
328 implemented in the operational model. The control of the heating steam temperature has been carried
329 out as follows: it is linearly reduced in a quantity proportional to the MED-TVC load according to
330 the following expression:

$$T_s = T_{s,nom} - \left(1 - \frac{q_m}{q_{m,nom}}\right) \cdot k_s \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

331 where $T_{s,nom}$ is the nominal heating steam temperature, $q_{m,nom}$ is the nominal mass flow rate of
332 motive steam and q_m is the motive steam mass flow rate at the different loads of the MED-TVC
333 plant, from the nominal one to the value corresponding to 40%. Finally, k_s is a constant determined
334 to obtain a heating steam temperature of 60 °C for the lowest load of the MED-TVC unit (40%).
335 Notice that the decrease of the heating steam temperature can be done in real desalination plants by
336 adjusting the amount of distillate entering the desuperheater.

337

338

Figure 7. Algorithm developed for the operation control of the MED-TVC unit.

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Notice that the rejected cooling mass flow rate is used in the algorithm as an internal control variable. Δ_F and Δ_{cw} are the step change in the feedwater (q_F) and rejected cooling (q_{cw}) mass flow rates, respectively.

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Figure 8 shows an example of the MED-TVC unit operation in off-design conditions between 100% and 40% of the nominal mass flow rate of motive steam using the adjustment algorithms described above. This case corresponds to the integration of the MED-TVC unit into the power block using steam from the high pressure extraction HP2, and a thermal load of 37.5% in the power block. As can be seen, the feedwater mass flow rate is perfectly controlled in order to maintain the brine salinity in the first effect below 70,000 ppm, keeping the temperature of the end condenser near to its design value (37 °C).

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350 **Figure 8.** Variation of the brine salinity in the first effect, feedwater mass flow rate and temperature
 351 of the end condenser as function of the motive steam mass flow rate for the 37.5% of the load in the
 352 power block when the MED-TVC is integrated using steam from HP2.

353 3. Results

354 Figure 9 shows the variation of the steam mass flow rate entering the first feedwater heater (LP P1)
 355 with the load of the power block, for each coupling arrangement. In this figure, the limit loads that
 356 allow a constant motive steam mass flow rate for the thermocompressor equal to that at nominal
 357 conditions are shown. As mentioned above, this limit is established by the mass flow rate of steam
 358 available in the first low pressure feedwater heater LP P1 that becomes lower than 0.1 kg/s. As
 359 depicted, in all cases this happens for loads roughly less than 50% of the nominal value. Particularly,
 360 for the HP2, HP1, DEA and LP3 steam extractions the minimum feasible loads are 40%, 42.5%,
 361 42.5% and 45%, respectively. The decrease of the steam supplied to LP P1 is due to the fact that the
 362 motive steam mass flow rate to the thermocompressor is kept constant while the steam in the power
 363 block decreases linearly with the load of the power block.

364

365 **Figure 9.** Variation of the mass flow rate of steam in the feedwater heater LP1 with the load.

366 Once the limit loads of the power block were achieved, the motive steam mass flow rate was reduced
 367 by steps of 0.5 kg/s until the steam to LP P1 was above 0.1 kg/s or the minimum load of the MED-
 368 TVC operation (40%) was reached. Simulations of the MED-TVC unit integrated into the power
 369 block also resulted in certain feasible minimum loads of the power block. These minimum limits are
 370 those ones that allowed the convergence of the model and were 25% for all steam extractions, except
 371 for LP3, that was 27.5%.

372 Table 4 shows some of the variables obtained from the simulations: motive steam pressure, motive
 373 steam mass flow rate, suction and compressed steam mass flow rates, mass flow rate of steam
 374 entering the LP P1 feedwater heater, net power generated, total fresh water produced, *GOR*, recovery
 375 ratio (*RR*), brine salinity in the first effect, heating steam temperature, temperature of the last effect,
 376 compression ratio (*CR*), expansion ratio (*ER*) and entrainment ratio (*Ra*), for six selected points of
 377 load of the power block in each coupling arrangement: over nominal conditions (120%), the nominal
 378 operation (100%), half-load operation (50%), the minimum load for which the motive steam nominal
 379 mass flow rate can be maintained (see Figure 9), the load from which the nominal motive steam mass
 380 flow rate has been decreased by steps of 0.5 kg/s, and finally the minimum load achievable by the
 381 power block. It can be seen that the freshwater production slightly decreases when the motive steam
 382 mass flow rate is kept constant. This is due to the fact that the decrease in the motive steam pressure
 383 causes

a

Table 4. Selected operation points for the four coupling arrangements considered.

	Load (%)	p_m (bar)	q_m (kg/s)	q_{suc} (kg/s)	q_{comp} (kg/s)	q_{LP1} (kg/s)	P_{We} (kW)	q_D (m ³ /d)	GOR (-)	RR (-)	X_1 (ppm)	T_s (°C)	T_{12} (°C)	CR (-)	ER (-)	Ra (-)
HP2	120	53.98	7.691	4.507	12.2	2.24	52464.1	9848.8	14.7	0.313	66024	70	36.91	4.51	781	1.706
	100	45.40	7.691	4.446	12.14	1.77	44094.4	9823.2	14.67	0.312	65899	70	37	4.49	653.6	1.73
	50	20.60	7.691	4.083	11.77	0.40	19692.9	9651.4	14.41	0.319	66476	70	37.36	4.40	290.4	1.884
	40	15.16	7.691	3.927	11.62	0.10	14238.2	9569.8	14.28	0.324	66969	70	37.5	4.36	212.0	1.959
	37.5	14.81	6.691	3.682	10.37	0.12	13552.9	8783	15.07	0.336	67604	67.8	37.09	4.09	213.7	1.817
	25	11.40	3.191	2.41	5.601	0.10	8979.2	5228.2	18.81	0.383	69785	60.3	37.88	2.91	164.4	1.324
HP1	120	24.58	7.757	4.612	12.37	2.24	53540.2	9640.7	14.27	0.313	66161	70	36.84	3.99	314.5	1.682
	100	20.60	7.757	4.543	12.3	1.76	45058.3	9593.5	14.2	0.312	65907	70	37	3.96	261.3	1.708
	50	8.99	7.757	4.105	11.86	0.37	20514.2	9370.3	13.87	0.323	66933	70	37.41	3.85	111.1	1.89
	42.5	7.15	7.757	4.161	11.92	0.14	16438.7	9385.6	13.89	0.324	67026	70	37.37	3.87	88.69	1.864
	40	6.78	7.257	4.009	11.27	0.12	15360.9	8999.8	14.24	0.331	67537	68.9	37.14	3.76	85.69	1.81
	25	5.11	3.103	2.318	5.421	0.11	9459.2	4853.9	17.96	0.380	69514	60	38.32	2.58	66.11	1.339
DEA	120	10.65	7.785	4.71	12.49	2.25	54853.4	9324.5	13.75	0.312	65942	70	37.03	3.49	119.2	1.653
	100	8.75	7.785	4.783	12.57	1.76	46341.3	9344.1	13.78	0.311	65918	70	37	3.50	98.24	1.628
	50	3.73	7.785	4.041	11.83	0.36	21641.3	8998.4	13.27	0.330	67476	70	37.6	3.36	40.15	1.926
	42.5	2.93	7.785	3.778	11.56	0.12	17569.4	8868.5	13.07	0.336	67876	70	37.85	3.30	31.03	2.061
	40	2.79	7.285	3.626	10.91	0.10	16419.4	8486.3	13.37	0.343	68399	68.9	37.64	3.22	30.14	2.009
	25	2.18	3.114	2.225	5.339	0.10	9886.2	4577.3	16.87	0.381	69479	60	38.66	2.32	25.34	1.4
LP3	120	4.43	8.377	4.358	12.73	2.22	55930.3	9498.4	13.02	0.315	66612	70	36.6	3.54	50.29	1.922
	100	3.63	8.377	4.178	12.55	1.73	47409.0	9384.6	12.86	0.312	65919	70	36.99	3.47	40.35	2.005
	50	1.50	8.377	3.02	11.4	0.31	22751.8	8857.5	12.13	0.340	68182	70	37.92	3.25	15.63	2.774
	45	1.27	8.377	2.776	11.15	0.15	20066.7	8737.2	11.97	0.345	68495	70	38.17	3.20	13.03	3.017
	42.5	1.22	7.877	2.691	10.57	0.12	18837.8	8387.2	12.22	0.354	69128	69.0	37.94	3.13	12.78	2.927
	27.5	0.97	3.877	1.997	5.874	0.10	11622.0	5050.8	14.96	0.383	69760	61.1	38.46	2.40	11.12	1.941

384 reduction in the suction steam, which leads to lower compressed steam flow rate and therefore to a
 385 lower distillate production.

386 However, the freshwater production suffers a rapid drop when the motive steam mass flow rate is
 387 diminished from its nominal value, as can be seen in Figure 10 where it has been represented the
 388 freshwater and power production for all the feasible operation points and for each steam extraction
 389 considered. As an example, in the case of using steam from HP2, if the power block load decreases
 390 from 100 to 40%, the freshwater production is reduced nearly 2.6% (from 9823.2 to 9569.8 m³/d),
 391 while a reduction of the power block load from 100% to 25% generates a drop in the freshwater yield
 392 of 47% approximately, from 9823.2 to 5228.2 m³/d (in this latter case the motive steam mass flow
 393 rate is reduced by 40%). Notice that the curves of water production for HP1 and DEA steam
 394 extractions suffer a change of tendency at power block loads of 47.5% and 105%, which is explained
 395 by a discontinuity in the correlations of the thermocompressor model (the performance equation
 396 changes at $ER = 100$), as reported as well in [17].

397

398 **Figure 10.** Power and freshwater production for each steam extraction considered as function of the
 399 power block load.

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401 Regarding the power, it is observed that it decreases linearly with the load of the power block until
 402 the load limit of the power block at which the motive steam feeding the MED-TVC unit has to be
 403 decreased. At this point, it is observed a trend change and the decrease in the power production

404 becomes smaller. It can be due to the fact that the penalty rate in the power production decreases
 405 with the mass flow rate of the motive steam for the thermocompressor. For instance, a reduction of
 406 the thermal power load from 42.5 to 40% leads to a decrease in the power production from 15,624 to
 407 14,238 kW (8.9%), while if the thermal power load is reduced from 40 to 37.5%, the decrease in the
 408 power production goes from 14,238 to 13,553 kW (4.8%). On the other hand, from a comparison
 409 between the coupling arrangements, it is seen that the use of high pressure steam from HP2 to feed
 410 the MED-TVC unit leads to the maximum amount of freshwater for all the loads of the power block
 411 but also to the lowest power production. On the contrary, as expected, the use of steam from the low
 412 pressure extraction LP3 generates the lowest freshwater production but the maximum power for all
 413 the load range.

414 Figure 11 depicts the variation of the motive steam mass flow rate and the Gain Output Ratio (*GOR*)
 415 with the load of the power block. As it can be seen, the *GOR* follows an evolution roughly constant
 416 from 120% to the limit load of the power block, when the motive steam mass flow rate has to be
 417 decreased. More importantly, variable area thermocompressors help to even increase the *GOR* when
 418 the motive steam flow is strongly decreased (power block load below 50%). As observed, the highest
 419 *GOR* was achieved using high pressure steam from HP2 extraction, while the lowest *GOR* was
 420 obtained using steam from the lowest pressure extraction LP3.

421

422 **Figure 11.** *GOR* and motive steam mass flow rate and as function of the power block load.

423 The variation of the feedwater mass flow rate and the brine salinity in the first effect as function of
 424 the load of the power block, for each steam extraction, is represented in Figure 12, where the control
 425 algorithm developed has been used.

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Figure 12. Feedwater mass flow rate and brine salinity in the first effect as function of the power block load.

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On the other hand, as observed in Figure 13, the control loop also allows to maintain the last effect temperature (T_{12}) (which is equivalent to the end condenser temperature) around the nominal value ($37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), as long as the mass flow rate of feedwater was enough to maintain the brine salinity in the first effect under the maximum limit. In the same figure it has been represented the variation of the heating steam temperature with the power block load. In this case, while the motive steam mass flow rate is equal to the nominal, the heating steam temperature is kept constant and equal to its nominal value ($70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), but when the motive steam mass flow rate decreases, the heating steam temperature is reduced according to Eq. 2).

437

438 **Figure 13.** Last effect temperature and heating steam temperature as function of the power block
 439 load.

440 **4. Conclusions**

441 In this paper a parametric analysis of the coupling between a MED-TVC unit and a Rankine cycle
 442 power block with variable nozzle thermocompressors has been carried out, in order to investigate the
 443 operational limits of the integration of both systems. Four different coupling arrangements have been
 444 considered, corresponding with four steam extractions from the power block feeding the
 445 thermocompressor of the MED-TVC unit: two from the high pressure turbine (HP2, HP1) and two
 446 from the low pressure turbine (DEA, HP3). On one hand, the thermal load of the power block has
 447 been decreased up to the technical limit. On the other hand, the MED-TVC unit has been simulated
 448 at part load conditions when there was not enough steam available in the power block.

449 The main conclusions reached in this study are the following:

- 450 ■ The use of variable nozzle thermocompressors in a MED-TVC unit coupled to a Rankine
 451 cycle power block would allow us to maintain the motive steam mass flow rate constant when
 452 the power load decreases (with sliding pressure regulation), thus operating the MED-TVC
 453 unit near to nominal conditions as long there is enough steam available in the power block .
- 454 ■ There are bottom limits of the load in each coupling arrangement considered for which the
 455 steam entering the last feedwater heater of the low pressure turbine (LP P1) is near to zero. In

456 those cases, the motive steam mass flow rate has to be decreased and consequently the fresh
457 water production is considerably reduced. However, variable area thermocompressors help to
458 even increase the *GOR* in these cases. As an example, in the case of using steam from HP2,
459 when the load decreases from 100% to 40% the freshwater reduction is of 2.6% and the *GOR*
460 decreases 2.66%; when the load decreases from 100% to 25%, the freshwater reduction is of
461 47%, while the *GOR* decreases increases 28.8%. The operation limits of the power block are
462 40, 42.5, 42.5 and 45% of the load for the HP2, HP1, DEA and LP3 steam extractions of the
463 high pressure and low pressure turbines, respectively. The nominal *GOR* are 14.67, 14.2,
464 13.78 and 12.86, and they are reduced only to 14.28, 13.89, 13.07 and 11.97 for those lowest
465 operation points maintaining the nominal motive steam mass flow rate.

- 466 ■ When the motive steam mass flow rate or pressure of the thermocompressor is reduced from
467 its nominal value, the MED-TVC unit works in off-design conditions and the brine salinity
468 increases. In order to control the maximum value of the brine salinity in the unit and the brine
469 temperature in the last effect, the feedwater mass flow rate and heating steam temperature
470 need to be properly adjusted.

- 471 ■ Regarding the coupling arrangements considered in the study case, the use of steam from the
472 highest pressure extraction considered (HP2) leads to the maximum freshwater production,
473 ranging from 9823.2 to 5228.2 m³/d for a variation of the power block load between 100%
474 and 25% (steam extraction pressures of 45.4 and 11.4 bar, respectively), and the smallest
475 power generation, from 44.094 to 8.979 MW_e in all the load range. The contrary occurs when
476 using steam from the lowest pressure extraction selected (LP3), with water and power
477 productions ranging from 9384.6 to 5050.8 m³/d, and from 47.409 to 11.662 MW_e,
478 respectively, for power block loads between 100% and 27.5% (steam extraction pressures of
479 3.63 and 0.97 bar, respectively).

480

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